

Studies on N-Substituted Salicyl-hydroxamic Acid as Metal-Complexing Ligand: Part II. Titanium Complexes

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By Job's method the composition of the compound formed between Ti(IV) and N-phenyl-salicyl-hydroxamic Acid (RH₂) in aqueous ethanol (1:1) at 0.824 (N)HCl medium (pH 0.5), has been found to be metal-ligand ratio 1:2. But in presence of EDTA at pH 6.6 another compound Ti(RH)₂OH has been isolated. The precipitation of this compound has been found to be quantitative and the estimation of titanium by weighing the precipitate has been made. Although Fe (III) and Al(III) compounds are not precipitated under this condition but higher results were obtained in the estimation of Ti(IV) in presence of Fe (III) and Al (III).

In our previous communication¹, it was reported that N-phenyl-salicyl-hydroxamic acid (RH₂) complexes many metal ions and some of the complexes were isolated. The titanium complex could not be isolated in pure state. So it is worthwhile to study the formation of titanium complexes in solution by the application of Job's method of continued variation². However a titanium compound at pH 6.6 in presence of EDTA has been isolated and its composition has been determined by analysis. The precipitation of the compound under above condition has been found to be quantitative and titanium is therefore possible to estimate gravimetrically on weighing the precipitate after drying at 95-100°C. At the same pH values, Fe(III) and Al(III) compounds were not precipitated. But when Ti (IV) was attempted to estimate in their presence, higher results were obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

A. *Study of Ti(IV) complexes by Job's method.* The composition of the complex of Ti(IV) with the reagent in solution was studied spectrophotometrically by the Job's method of continued variation. The absorption of the mixture of equimolar solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ and $0.5 \times 10^{-4}M$) of Ti(IV) and the reagent in aqueous ethanol(1:1) after adjustment of acidity to 0.824(N) HCl (pH 0.5) and dilution to 25 ml with aqueous ethanol (1:1) were measured at 480 m μ , 450 m μ and 420 m μ . Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 show the graphical representations of the optical densities (after zero error correction) against the volume (in ml) of the reagent used. It appears from the figure that the complex has a metal-ligand ratio 1:2. There are also indications of the formation of complexes in higher ratios, but such formation could not be definitely proved. The absorbance of the mixtures were measured in 1 cm-cell. Spectral curves of mixtures containing different proportions

1. Ghosh and Bhattacharyya, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 311.
2. Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, (10), 9, 113.

of Ti(IV) and RH_2 solutions in aqueous ethanol(1:1) after adjustment of acidity to 0.824(N) HCl and dilution to 25 ml with aqueous ethanol (1:1) are shown in Fig. 3.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

B. *Study of Ti(IV) compound in presence of EDTA.* A compound was prepared by adding excess reagent (10 ml of about 0.2M RH_2 solution in dilute ammonia) to Ti(IV) solution (10 ml of 0.0375M Ti(IV) in dilute HCl) in presence of EDTA (10 ml of about 0.1M EDTA solution in water). When addition was complete with constant stirring, the solution was treated with aqueous ammonia and the pH was made to about 6-7, indicated by the change in colour of the methyl red to yellow. The precipitate formed was allowed to settle down for half an hour. It was then filtered through sintered glass crucible (No. 4), washed with water and dried at 95°-100°C. (Found: Ti—6.33; N—5.34%. $Ti(RH)_2(OH)$ requires Ti—6.41; N—5.6%).

FIG. 3

C. *Gravimetric Estimation of Ti(IV).* Ti(IV) can be estimated quantitatively with this reagent in presence of EDTA. Ti(IV) solution (0.0375M) in presence of about 2 times excess of EDTA solution (about 0.1M, 3.8586 gm dissolved in 100 ml of water) was

treated with about 5 times excess of RH_3 solution (about 0.2M, nearly 5 gm in 100 ml; reagent dissolved in least quantity of dilute ammonia and then desired volume was made up with water) and the solution was made alkaline to methyl red by addition of dilute ammonia. When pH was near about 6-7 (pH of the filtrate was found to be 6.6 on measuring with a pH-meter) the precipitate was allowed to settle down for half an hour. The precipitate was then filtered through sintered glass crucible (No. 4), washed with water, dried at 95° - $100^{\circ}C$ and weighed. The results are stated in Table I.

TABLE I

Ti(IV) solution in aqueous HCl. 0.0375M, in ml.	RH_3 solution in aqueous NH_3 , about 0.2M in gm.	Wt. of the precipitate found; gm.	Wt. of the compound required by the formula $Ti(RH)_3$ (OH) gm.	Percentage of error
10.0	0.5506	0.2835	0.2810	+0.88
5.0	0.2819	0.1396	0.1405	-0.64
5.5	0.3310	0.1543	0.1546	-0.19
4.5	0.3310	0.1267	0.1265	+0.15

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